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MOTIVATION AS A POSITIVE ATTITUDE FOR SUCCESSFUL LEARNING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ANNOTATION

It is generally acknowledged that two key factors that contribute to language learners' success are their motivation and attitude. Reviewing and talking about motivation and attitude in language learning is the purpose of this article. Particularly, the research gives light on how scholars within the field perceive these two components, as well as how the two parts are combined in language learning.

Language teachers should gain a deeper understanding of the two ideas from the discussions.

Key words: *acknowledged, motivation, attitude, configuration, conceptualized.*

INTRODUCTION

(instrumental motivation) (Dörnyei, 1994). They both maybe , in return, enhanced by better proficiency and higher achievement in the target language learning goals also proved to break up into different motivation clusters, the definition of which varies depending upon the socio-cultural setting in which motivation clusters have been identified, such as intrinsic and extrinsic motivations which were proposed as- intrinsic motivation refers to doing something because it is inherently interesting or enjoyable, and extrinsic motivation refers to doing no extrinsic or intrinsic goals for learning a language.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The majority of people in the language teaching profession are aware that when attitudes are positive and motivation is high, students have a greater potential for learning. This straightforward observation is supported by research on the relationship between positive attitudes and mastering a second language, but it's crucial to realize that there are a lot of variables at play because we're talking about intricate social and

psychological facets of human behavior. For example, a student's attitudes toward the target language, the target language speakers and their culture, the social value of learning a second language, and the student's attitudes toward themselves as members of their own culture can all have an impact on their ability to learn a second language (Ellis 1994). Furthermore, teachers of English as a foreign language (EFL) should be aware that all students have attitudes toward learning, both positive and negative, to varied degrees. The positive attitudes can be modified through deliberate teaching strategies, such as the use of resources and activities that foster in students an "understanding and appreciation of the foreign culture" (Brown 2000, 181).

Classroom action research is a helpful approach with well-defined steps that enables teachers to find, look into, apply solutions to, report on, and discuss findings in order to provide suggestions for better teaching practices and educational policies. Attitudes and language acquisition as noted by Brown (2000), attitudes are both cognitive and affective, meaning they are connected to both feelings and ideas. How one approaches learning is determined by their attitudes. Early experiences and interactions with people from different social and cultural backgrounds, as well as parents and peers, all have an impact on the formation of attitudes. As such, attitudes "become a component of one's understanding of oneself, of others, and of the society in which one lives" (Brown 2000, 180). Language acquisition can be hampered by unfavorable attitudes toward the target group and language, which frequently result from stereotypes and a cursory acquaintance with the target culture. On the other hand, a positive attitude toward the target language and the group promotes language acquisition success. After reviewing a number of studies on the subject, Brown (2000) draws the conclusion that "positive attitudes towards the self, the native language group, and the target language group enhanced proficiency" (181). Students who approach language learning positively are rewarded for their success, while those who approach it negatively may not advance and may even become more pessimistic about language learning. Effective language teaching strategies can help students develop a more positive attitude towards the language they are learning, as experience has the power to modify attitudes.

Motivation is essential for successful learning. Experts have varied definitions of motivation. Hayikaleng, Nair, and Krishnasamy (2016) suggest that motivation is vital for students' success in English language studies.

Motivation refers to what drives a person to repeat an activity and vice versa (Alizadeh, 2016).

Furthermore, motivation and academic success as measured by grade point average are positively connected at all educational levels, from elementary to college, according to Tambunan & Siregar (2016).

It is clear from the above explanation that motivation is the result of attempt plus desire, which provides people with the means to achieve their goals of learning toward an objective and provides the rationale behind their actions.

Teachers should be aware of significance of motivation in learners' language learning and through some changes they can help learners increase their motivation (Alizadeh, 2016).

Integrative motivation

Integrative motivation refers to a learner's desire to acquire the target language in order to better understand and interact with speakers of the language who may differ in their cultural background (Rehman, et al. 2014).

Instrumental motivation

According to Alizadeh (2016), instrumental motivation refers to learners' desire to assimilate into the second language group's culture and engage in social interactions there. Mihalas (2009) contends that they take note of both the potential positive effects and negative ones, depending on how well the relationships are going. According to the authors, a teacher's relationship with their students can affect the students' desire to make an effort to grow and learn more. The teacher-student relationship is influenced by several factors, including the teacher's respect, ability to be trusted, and ease of communication (Mihalas, et al.). 2009).

In addition to helping students discover their own motivational processes, teachers should also support their students in determining what motivates them. This study's motivation identifies factors that draw in students. Either intrinsic or extrinsic motivation in the students may be the cause.

Intrinsic Motivation

Hayikaleng, Nair and Krishnasamy (2016) state that intrinsic motivation (IM) in language learning refers to motivation to involve in an activity because the activity is enjoyable and interesting to take part. A person may be motivated by a desire to feel better about themselves or by the enjoyment of the learning activity. The students are excited about studying English because it is an innate desire of theirs.

Extrinsic Motivation

According to Hayikaleng, Nair, and Krishnasamy (2016), extrinsic motivation (EM) is any behavior that a person engages in to avoid punishment or to obtain rewards like higher pay or better grades. Here, the students' external motivation to study English is stoked by their desire to apply for jobs, pass exams, and so forth.

Motivation is essential to the enthusiasm of learning, as the lack of it will make it impossible for someone to carry out learning activities. In order to decide how hard students will work to learn, motivation is necessary. According to Lai (2011), one

element influencing students' motivation is reward. Depending on the kind of recognition and the environment in which it is offered, rewards can either increase or decrease motivation.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The current studies on the use of motivation in learning and teaching

Since motivation is widely recognized as having a significant role in learning, an increasing number of researchers are concentrating on the actual use of motivation in language learning and teaching environments. Today's instructional approach is based on the students-centered teaching paradigm, especially in developed nations. Thus, cooperative learning has been included into the curriculum. In fact, during the past 20 years, the use of small groups in the classroom to accomplish shared learning objectives through cooperation has had an almost unheard-of impact on English language education. In-depth studies have consistently shown that this type of learning is a very successful classroom intervention, outperforming the majority of traditional instruction methods in terms of learning gains and student achievement, higher-order thinking, positive attitudes toward learning, increased motivation, and improved teacher-student and student-student relationships along with improved interpersonal skills and higher self-esteem on the part of the student. What matters most, though, is that peer cooperation creates the motivational system in psychological processes related to cooperative language learning (Dornyei, 1977). Second, one characteristic of cooperative learning is the Norm and Reward system. Under it, students are driven to succeed by their desire to avoid punishment for not contributing fairly to the group's success as well as their need for social acceptance. Thirdly, autonomy-supporting classroom environments in cooperatively structured classrooms result in higher levels of long-term, intrinsic motivation (Ames and Ames, 1984).

This idea that autonomy is fundamental to learning motivation is also at the heart of Deci and Ryan's (1985) seminal "self-determination" theory, which has demonstrated a strong positive influence on motivation in L2 contexts. The remarkable findings of a major study on the role of motivation in CL by Sharan and Shaulov (1990), who found that the "motivation to learn" factor accounted for more than half of the variance in achievement in three academic subjects, can be explained by the multitude of different motivational aspects that CL significantly affects. Such a significant impact is extremely uncommon in studies of motivation in several. Thus, it is possible to observe the effectiveness of the motivational system that is fostered in cooperative settings.

CONCLUSION

More than half of the variance in achievement in three academic subjects was caused by the "motivation to learn" factor, according to a major study on the role of motivation in CL. This finding can be explained by the variety of motivational aspects that CL significantly affects. Studies on motivation have shown that such a significant impact is extremely uncommon. As a result, it is evident how successful the motivational system is encouraged in cooperative settings.

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